

MENTORSHIP-SCAFFOLDING AS PREDICTOR OF TEACHERS' JOB PRODUCTIVITY IN SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN LAGOS

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the mentorship scaffolding as predictor of Teachers' job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive research design. The population of this study comprised of all the 8510 teachers, 652 Vice Principals and 326 Principals in the Public Senior Secondary Schools within the six Educational Districts in Lagos State, Nigeria. A-15 items Mentorship Scaffolding Questionnaire (MSQ) and 20-items Teacher's Job Productivity Questionnaire (TJPQ) was used to collect data for this research. Using split half method, Cronbach Alpha was used to measure the internal consistency co-efficient of the Mentorship Scaffolding and Teachers Job Productivity questionnaires. The 15 items on Mentorship Scaffolding, 20 items on Teachers Job Productivity shows the instruments are reliable. Research questions were analysed using mean and standard deviation while the stated hypotheses were tested using Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation at 0.05 level of significance.

KEYWORDS

Mentorship Scaffolding, Teachers' Job Productivity, Secondary school Education.

INTRODUCTION

In any developing country, including Nigeria, there is an ever increasing need for re-training of teachers in order to facilitate efficient and effective implementation of curriculum for teaching productivity and a functional Nigerian educational system. Similarly, the rate of academic development and the increasing demand with regards to knowledge-based economy and technology advancement require a constantly and regular update of the teaching workforce (Awodiji et al., 2020). The teaching profession is essentially based on knowledge, teaching strategies, education psychology, care, ethics and general conduct (Mukwevho et al., 2020). Teachers have been likened to artists, particularly when some literature refers to the process of teaching as being an art rather than a science. A teacher is the only person who is capable of imparting knowledge and shaping the youths to the wider scope of knowledge (Mukwevho et al., 2020). Teachers are capable of living and moulding the youths such that their power is paramount as they determine the fate of the society. Both teachers and parents live with the children for a long time and hence they are capable of imparting knowledge, skills and values that cannot be easily challenged by the society (Dorner et al., 2021).

Framework for Action (2020) emphasised the need of a stimulating pedagogy. It is the teaching and learning process that brings the curriculum to life that determines what happens in the classroom and subsequently the quality of the learning outcomes. Quality in education can be regarded as the ability of an educational system to meet the ever-dynamic demand, requirements and expectations of educational customers (that is, students, teachers, parents, governments, employers and institutions) (OECD, 2022). Thus, teachers who are the bedrock

of ensuring a quality Education system have to acquire required skills and are expected to be exposed to mentorship and training due to the changing in job content and environment which improves their Professional development and effective evaluation of their job productivity (Rahman et al, 2015).

Mentoring is commonly agreed as the process which includes various developmental phases of the mentoring relationship, the dynamics of the mentoring relationship itself, and the application of cognitive developmental theory to the mentoring process (Wahab et al., 2020). According to Williams et al., (2013), mentoring encompasses psychosocial and career functions, where career-related functions foster mentees' professional development and psychosocial functions and increase their self-efficacy and professional identity. In higher education, these functions are synthesized into three broader areas, namely, educational, professional, and psychosocial development (Chiekem, 2015). Mentoring functions of educational development focus on academic program planning, and formal and informal teaching/learning moments.

In education, mentoring is a complex and multi-dimensional process of guiding, teaching, influencing and supporting a beginning or new teacher. It is generally accepted that a mentor teacher leads, guides and advises another teacher more junior in experience in a work situation characterized by mutual trust and belief.

Typically, mentoring programmes pair novice teachers with more experienced teachers who can ably explain school policies, regulations and procedures; share methods, materials and other resources; help solve problems in teaching and learning; provide personal and professional support; and guide the growth of the new teacher through reflection, collaboration, and shared inquiry (Pylman & Bell, 2021).

Scaffolding draws on the work of Vygotsky (1978), although the term first came into use in an article written by Wood, Bruner, and Ross (1976). In education, scaffolding is a metaphor for a structure that is put in place to help learners reach their goals and is removed bit by bit when it is no longer needed, much like a physical scaffold is placed around a building that is under construction and removed as the building nears completion. In practice, however, scaffolding is a learner-centered strategy whose success is dependent upon its adaptability to the learner's needs. Additionally, scaffolding is much more than a physical support in a learning context, addressing student learning of concepts, procedures, strategies, and metacognitive skills (Wahab et al., 2020). Scaffolding has been described as either directive or supportive, depending on where the impetus for the support originates (Torres et al., 2021).

Typically, mentorship scaffolding in education is the process of pairing novice teachers with more experienced teachers who can ably explain school policies, regulations and procedures; share methods, materials and other resources; help solve problems in teaching and learning; provide personal and professional support; and guide the growth of the new teacher through reflection, collaboration, and shared inquiry (Rahman et al., 2015). Mentorship Scaffolding is one of the ways to improve both teachers' Job productivity.

Despite the significance of mentorship scaffolding in enhancing teaching skills and job performance, there exists a dearth of comprehensive research examining their combined impact on the job productivity of teachers in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State. While individual studies have explored these elements separately, an integrated understanding of how mentorship scaffolding affect teacher productivity remains limited.

This study aims to address this gap by investigating the influence of mentorship scaffolding, on the job productivity of teachers in public senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. Key challenges faced by teachers, such as curriculum changes, classroom management, technology integration, and student diversity, are ever-evolving. Thus, the question of how mentorship scaffolding programs can be tailored to meet these challenges and maximize teacher productivity becomes critical.

Based on the purpose of the study, the following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the level of awareness and operation of Mentorship scaffolding among teachers in Lagos State Senior Secondary Schools, Nigeria?
2. What is the level of Job productivity among teachers in Lagos State senior secondary schools, Nigeria?
3. Is there any relationship between mentorship scaffolding and job productivity among teachers in Lagos State Senior Secondary Schools, Nigeria?

The following null hypothesis is formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

HO₁: There is no significant relationship between mentorship scaffolding and Job productivity among teachers in Lagos state senior secondary school, Nigeria.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study adopted descriptive research design. The population of this study comprised of all the 8510 teachers, 652 Vice Principals and 326 Principals in the Public Senior Secondary Schools within the six Educational Districts in Lagos State, Nigeria. Total sample of 370 teachers, 196 Principals, and 248 Vice Principals were selected from the six Education Districts in Lagos State (namely Education District I, II, III, IV, V and VI) using Research Advisor Standard Sample Table.

Table 1. The sample size of Principals, Vice Principals and Teachers selected from the Education Districts in Lagos State, Nigeria.

S/N	Education District	Principals and Vice Principals	Teachers	Total Number
1	Education District I	65	43	108
2	Education District II	72	52	124
3	Education District III	45	25	70
4	Education District IV	91	37	128
5	Education District V	102	98	200
6	Education District VI	37	103	140
Total		412	358	770

The research instruments used for this study are two self-structured questionnaires: Mentorship Scaffolding Questionnaire (MSQ) which was responded to by Teachers (shows

73.1% reliability). Another instrument is Teacher’s Job Productivity Questionnaire (TJPQ) filled by the Principals and Vice Principals (shows 72.2% reliability). The biographical data were analysed using simple percentage. Research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation with graphical representations while research hypotheses were tested using Pearson’s Product-Moment Correlation and linear regression analysis on Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version23.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Distribution of the respondents Based on Education districts (Principals and Vice Principals).

Figure 1: Count of Education District of Principals & VicePrincipals

Figure 1 Shows that the percentage of respondents in Education District 5 were more than others.

Distribution of the respondents Based on Education districts (Teachers).

Figure 2: Count of Education District (Teachers)

Figure 2 Shows that the percentage of respondents in Education District 6 was more than others.

Distribution of respondents based on local Government in which schools are located

Figure 3: Count of Local Government in which your School is Located (Teachers)

Figure 3 Shows that the percentage of respondents in Schools located at Surulere Local Government was more than others.

Distribution of respondents based on principals and vice principals' teaching experience in the six education district (Principals & vice Principals).

Figure 4: Count of Teaching Experience (Principal & Vice Principal)

Figure 4 Shows that the percentage of respondents which intervals are between the range of 21-30yrs and (31 and above) years have the largest population.

Distribution of respondents based on principals and vice principals' teaching experience in the six education district (teachers).

Figure 5: Count of Teaching Experience of teachers

Figure 5 above shows the distribution of respondents based on the teaching experience of the teachers. The result shows that 40% of the respondents have 1 – 10yrs) range of teaching experience, 27% have the range of 11 -20yrs teaching experience, 22% have the range of 21 - 30yrs teaching experience while 11% of them have the range of 31 and above years of teaching experience. Figure 6 further shows that the percentage of respondents which intervals are between the ranges of 1 -10yrs have the largest population.

Distribution of respondents based on the age bracket of principals and vice principals in the six education district.

Figure 6: Count of Age Bracket of principals and vice principals

Figure 6 above shows the distribution of respondents based on the age bracket of principals and vice principals. The result shows that 2% of the respondents have the interval of 26–30yrs of age, 6% were between 31-35yrs of age, 10% were between 36-40yrs of age, 12% were between 41-45yrs of age, 17% were between 46-50yrs of age, 25% were between 51-55yrs of age, while 28% were between 56-60yrs of age. Figure 7 further shows that the percentage of respondents which age intervals are between the ranges of 56-60yrs have the largest population.

Distribution of respondents based on the age bracket of teachers in the six education district.

Figure 7: Count of Age Bracket of Teachers

Figure 7 above shows the distribution of respondents based on the age bracket of teachers. The data shows that 8% of the respondents were in the interval of 26–30yrs of age, 11% were between 31-35yrs of age, 27% were between 36-40yrs of age, 23% were between 41-45yrs of age, 20% were between 46-50yrs of age, 10% were between 51-55yrs of age, while 1% were between 56-60yrs of age. Figure 8 further shows that the percentage of respondents which age intervals were between 36-40yrs have the largest population.

Distribution of respondents based on educational qualifications of principals and vice principals in the six education district.

Figure 8: Count of Educational Qualifications of principals and vice principals

Figure 8 shows the distribution of respondents based on educational qualifications of principals and vice principals. The data shows that 6% of the respondents were certified with PHD certificate, 31% were M.A / M.Ed / MSc holders, while 63% of them were B.Ed/ B.A Ed / BSc (Ed) holders. Figure 9 further shows that the percentage of respondents certified with B.Ed/ B.A (Ed) / BSc (Ed) holders were more than others in the education districts.

Distribution of respondents based on educational qualifications of teachers in the six education district.

Figure 9: Count of Educational Qualifications of teachers

Figure 9 shows the distribution of respondents based on educational qualifications of teachers. The result shows that 62% of the respondents were certified with B.Ed/ B.A (Ed) / BSc (Ed) certificate, 33% were M.A / M.Ed / MSc holders, 3% were (NCE) holders while 2% of them were (PHD) holders. Figure 10 further shows that the percentage of respondents certified with B.Ed/ B.A (Ed) / BSc (Ed) holders were more than others in the education districts.

Answering of research questions

Answer to research questions one: What is the level of awareness and operation of Mentorship scaffolding among teachers in Lagos State Senior Secondary Schools, Nigeria? The answer to the question is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. The level of awareness and operation of Mentorship scaffolding among teachers in Lagos State Senior Secondary Schools , Nigeria.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Valid N (listwise)	358	29.09	9.129
Weighted Mean		3.19	

Table 2 above provides data for the answers to research question one. From the analysis above, the selected options was chosen by the respondents from the given items to know the level of awareness and operation of Mentorship scaffolding among teachers in Lagos State Senior Secondary Schools, Nigeria. Based on the research, the total mean level of awareness and operation of Mentorship scaffolding among teachers is 29.09 with standard deviation of 9.129 and weighted mean of 3.19.

Therefore, the research finds out that the mean of each item is below the average of the weighted mean. However, we can therefore conclude that there is low level awareness and operation of Mentorship scaffolding among teachers in Lagos State Senior Secondary Schools, Nigeria.

Answer to research questions two: What is the level of Job productivity among teachers in Lagos State senior secondary schools, Nigeria? The answer to the question is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. The level of Job productivity among teachers in Lagos State senior secondary schools, Nigeria.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Valid N (listwise)	412	37.51	12.577
Weighted Mean		2.98	

Table 3 above provides data for the answers to research question three. From the analysis above, the selected options was chosen by the respondents from the given items to know the level of Job productivity among teachers in Lagos State senior secondary schools, Nigeria. Based on the research, the total mean level of Job productivity among teachers is 37.51 with standard deviation of 12.577 and weighted mean of 2.98.

Therefore, the research finds out that the mean of each item is below the average of the weighted mean. However, we can therefore conclude that there is low level of Job productivity among teachers in Lagos State senior secondary schools, Nigeria.

Test of hypothesis

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between mentorship scaffolding and Job productivity among teachers in Lagos state senior secondary school, Nigeria.

Table 4. Relationship between mentorship scaffolding and Job productivity among teachers in Lagos state senior secondary school, Nigeria
Correlations

		Mentorship Scaffolding	Teachers' Job Productivity
Mentorship Scaffolding	Pearson Correlation	1	.848**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	412	412
Teachers' Job Productivity	Pearson Correlation	.848**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	412	412

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 shows the significant relationship between mentorship scaffolding and Job productivity among teachers in Lagos state senior secondary school, Nigeria. The relationship was investigated using Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient. Preliminary analyses were performed to ensure no violation of the assumptions of normality, linearity and homoscedasticity. There was a strong, positive correlation (relationship) between the two variables, $r = .848$, $n = 412$, $p < .0005$ with high levels of mentorship scaffolding associated with high level of Job productivity among teachers.

Furthermore, we can therefore reject the null hypothesis that stated that there is no significant relationship between mentorship scaffolding and Job productivity among teachers in Lagos state senior secondary school, Nigeria.

The study found that:

1. there is low level awareness and operation of Mentorship scaffolding among teachers in Lagos State Senior Secondary Schools, Nigeria;
2. there is low level of Job productivity among teachers in Lagos State senior secondary schools, Nigeria;
3. there is significant relationship between mentorship scaffolding and Job productivity among teachers in Lagos state senior secondary school, Nigeria;

Discussion

The study's primary objective was to look into the influence of mentorship scaffolding and professional development on job productivity among teachers in public secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study revealed that there is low level awareness and operation of Mentorship scaffolding among teachers in Lagos State senior secondary schools, Nigeria.

This finding is in tune with that of (Awodiji et al., 2020) which emphasises that a lot of graduate teachers find themselves under the leadership of school leaders who mentor them without building a scaffold for mentorship. This position is contrary to the position of Skills et al., (2020) that mentorship is consistently in practice among old and new teachers at all levels, though they may not be aware of term mentorship scaffolding but the features of mentorship scaffolding are in operation.

The findings shows that the level of Job productivity among teachers in Lagos State senior secondary schools, Nigeria is low. These clarifications are in line with the opinion of Limon (2020), he argued that for effective teachers' job productivity to be achieved by teachers, it must be viewed from three dimensions (task performance, contextual performance and adaptive performance) as developed by Bhat and Beri (2016) which include preparation for the lesson, instruction, student evaluation, commitment, extracurricular activities, effective monitoring and inspection, effective leadership, motivation and discipline. Kafui Agbozo, (2017) on the contrary, opines that teachers in Nigerian schooling system has improved overtime due to continuous training and supervision. The result of their improvement is evident in the appreciation of student performance in both internal and external examination. Among the findings of this study is that there is significant relationship between mentorship scaffolding and Job productivity among teachers in Lagos state senior secondary school, Nigeria. The findings of this research are in agreement with the findings of Purnama et al., (2021) research found that the School leadership can create a learning environment at schools by helping teachers to identify their developmental needs, by encouraging experimentation, finding and allocating resources to support teachers' learning, and by enhancing the implementation of new learning. This is contrary to the position of Imran Junejo et al., (2017) that newly inducted school teachers in developing countries usually lack adequate mentorship and lack adequate guidance and mentorship from superior subordinates. This is due to lack of adequate manpower.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the study highlights the crucial role of mentorship scaffolding in enhancing teachers' productivity in Lagos State Senior Secondary Schools, Nigeria. The findings demonstrate that when teachers receive adequate mentorship support they experience positive outcomes in various aspects of their teaching, leading to increased productivity. The study's results align with existing research emphasizing the significance of mentorship in improving teaching practices and student achievement. Therefore, it is crucial for educational institutions and policymakers in Lagos State to prioritize the establishment of comprehensive mentorship programmes.

The study findings suggest that mentorship scaffolding positively influences teachers' productivity by providing guidance, support, and opportunities for reflection and collaboration. Through mentorship relationships, experienced teachers can impart their knowledge, expertise, and best practices to new or less-experienced teachers, facilitating their professional growth and development.

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